

1 Nutrient deprivation results in activation of TSC and TBD family genes.
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7 We report here the discovery of TSC and TBD genes as essential components of a nutrient sensing
8 system that detects changes in nutrient (i.e., amino acid) uptake and interacts with the major cellular
9 systems that coordinate use of energy in the cell and homeostasis associated with energy, mTOR, AKT
10 and PI3K. In multiple cellular models of nutrient deprivation or amino acid restriction, or following genetic
11 depletion of cellular components that function in energy homeostasis, molecules encoded by TSC and
12 TBD family genes are activated and repressed consistent a function for these genes in a system that
13 coordinates nutrient availability in the cell with balance in cellular energy. We describe here *TSC22D3* and
14 *TBC1D15* as major components of the serum starvation response in human cells.
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